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[Cetta] Submission Acknowledgement External Inbox x

 Jayapangus Press cetta.jurnalilmupendidikan@gmail.com via penerbit.org to me Wed, Nov 2, 2022, 6:43 AM

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Ahmad:

Terima kasih telah mengirimkan naskah, "Madrasah and School Students on Online Learning Course Amid Outbreaks, Who're More Satisfied?" ke Cetta: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan. Dengan sistem manajemen jurnal online yang kami gunakan, Anda akan dapat melacak kemajuannya melalui proses editorial dengan masuk ke situs web jurnal:

URL pengiriman: <https://jayapanguspress.penerbit.org/index.php/cetta/authorDashboard/submission/2094>

Nama Pengguna: ahmadjuhaidi

Selanjutnya silahkan tonton vidio ini [Proses Submit Naskah di Jurnal](#) untuk mengetahui proses kelanjutan naskah yang sudah disubmit, walaupun nama jurnal berbeda namun langkahnya sama, karena masih dibawah Penerbit Cv. Jayapangus Press

Terima kasih telah mempertimbangkan jurnal ini sebagai tempat untuk publikasi.

Salam

Editor

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[Cetta] Editor Decision

18-11-2022 11:42 AM

Ahmad Juhaidi, Noor Hidayati, Hamdani, Maulida Rezkia, Ahmad Wafa Nizami:

We have reached a decision regarding your submission to Cetta: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan, "Madrasah and School Students on Online Learning Course Amid Outbreaks, Who're More Satisfied? ".

Our decision is: Revisions Required

Best regards

Editor

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Review

49

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[Cetta] Editor Decision

30-11-2022 02:25 AM

Ahmad Juhaidi, Noor Hidayati, Hamdani, Maulida Rezkia, Ahmad Wafa Nizami:

Kami telah mencapai keputusan terkait pengajuan Anda ke Cetta: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan, "Madrasah and School Students on Online Learning Course Amid Outbreaks, Who're More Satisfied? ".
Keputusan kami adalah : **Naskah diterima untuk diterbitkan**
Selanjutnya silahkan membayar biaya pemrosesan artikel (APC) sebesar Rp. 500.000.

Pembayaran dapat dilakukan transfer ke BNI No Rek. 0194823396 a.n. I Ketut Sudarsana

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Salam Hormat

Editor

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Review

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[Cetta] Editor Decision

02-02-2023 01:26 AM

Ahmad Juhaidi, Noor Hidayati, Hamdani, Maulida Rezkia, Ahmad Wafa Nizami:

The editing of your submission, "Madrasah and School Students on Online Learning Course Amid Outbreaks, Who're More Satisfied? ," is complete. We are now sending it to production.

Submission URL: <https://jayapanguspress.penerbit.org/index.php/cetta/authorDashboard/submission/2094>

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